

Socio-technical factors generating social debt

Table 4: Socio-technical Congruence factor.

Id	Cause and Primary studies
STCF1	Presence of the phenomenon known as obfuscated architecture, which arises when multiple subgroups emerge within a development network without a unified organizational and socio-technical vision. This impairs mutual understanding and hinders effective architectural communication [PS4, PS5, PS9, PS10, PS23].
STCF2	Imbalance in the architect's role, who must mediate between proposed technical solutions and the social and organizational challenges within the team [PS3, PS9, PS21].
STCF3	Deficiency in socio-technical congruence, understood as the lack of alignment between technical dependencies and social coordination mechanisms, which can negatively affect both software productivity and quality [PS3, PS23].
STCF4	Suboptimal interaction between architects, Product Owners, and development teams, resulting in architectural decisions that are disconnected from actual customer needs [PS21, PS40].
STCF5	Deficient socio-technical structures that hinder the creation of a cohesive work environment between technical and organizational components, thereby generating social debt [PS8, PS10].

Acronyms used: Socio-Technical Congruence Factor (STCF).